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POZIVAM ZA SVEDOKE SVE BOGOVE I
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PRIZIVANJE, PREMA SVOJIM MOĆIMA I
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OČUVATI...

AMA

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INTRAMEDULARNA FIKSACIJA TROHANTERIČNOG REGIONA FEMURA: PREDNOSTI I MANE - PREGLED LITERATURE

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SAŽETAK

Prelomi trohanterne regije se svrstavaju u grupu zdravstvenih problema koje za posledicu imaju invaliditet, promenjen kvalitet života kao i povećanje procenta mortaliteta. S obzirom na to da je životni vek produžen, broj starijih osoba je povećan a samim tim i učestalost trohanternih preloma je veća. Naš cilj je da se intramedularna fiksacija preloma trohanterne regije predstavi kao jedna od najsavremenijih metoda lečenja. Mnogobrojna savremena literatura opisuje da je intramedularni klin odličan za operativno lečenje trohanternih preloma femura, kao i da se sastoji od dva cefalična zavrtnja koji su međusobno u integrisanom delovanju. Korišćenjem ovog osteosintetskog materijala postiže se veliki stepen stabilnosti fragmenata a ujedno i eliminišu rotacione sile između glave i vrata femura. Lečenje preloma trohanterne regije femura upotrebom intra i ekstramedularne fiksacije je veliki izazov za operatora kako zbog anatomske specifičnosti regije, teškoća i komplikacija tokom operacije tako i pojave postoperativnih komplikacija. Najidealnije je ono sredstvo koje će se odupreti svim silama koje dovode do rotacije, promene angulacije fragmenata kao i medijalnom pomeranju osovine femura. Intramedularna fiksacija preloma transtrohanterične regije predstavlja savremenu metodu operativnog lečenja sa minimalnim kako intraoperativnim tako i postoperativnim komplikacijama.

Ključne reči: trohanterni prelom, femur, intramedularna fiksacija

SUMMARY

Fractures of the trochanteric region are classified as a group of health problems that result in disability, a changed quality of life, and an increase in the mortality rate. Given that life expectancy has increased, the number of older adults has also increased, and therefore, the frequency of trochanteric fractures is higher. Our goal is to present the intramedullary fixation of fractures of the trochanteric region as one of the most modern methods of treatment. Numerous contemporary studies describe that the intramedullary nail is excellent for the operative treatment of trochanteric femoral fractures, and that it consists of two cephalic screws that are in an integrated action with each other. The use of this osteosynthetic material achieves a high degree of stability of the fragments and at the same time eliminates the rotational forces between the bone and the neck of the femur. Treatment of fractures in the trochanteric region of the femur using both intra- and extramedullary fixation poses a significant challenge for the operator due to the anatomical specificity of the area, the potential difficulties and complications that can arise during surgery, and the risk of postoperative complications. The ideal tool is the one that resists all forces leading to rotation, change in the angulation of the fragments, as well as medial displacement of the femoral shaft. Intramedullary fixation of fractures of the transtrochanteric region represents a modern method of operative treatment with minimal both intraoperative and postoperative complications.

Keywords: trochanteric fracture, femur, intramedullary fixation

Introduction

Fractures of the trochanter region are classified as a group of health problems that result in

disability, a change in quality of life, and an increase in mortality rates. Given that life expectancy has increased, the number of older adults has also increased, and therefore, the frequency of trochanteric fractures is higher [1]. Fractures of the trochanteric region comprise 50% of all

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hip fractures, of which 40% are unstable. They belong to the group of extracapsular fractures and are most common in the elderly population. Patients are exposed to forces of lower intensity, and it should be emphasized that the bones in women have changed structures due to demineralization resulting from osteoporosis. They mostly occur as a result of falling from the same level, such as from a bed or chair. Of course, since they are older adults, if their health condition is satisfactory, surgery is often the first choice of treatment. The ideal is to operate within the first 24 hours to reduce mortality rates and postoperative complications [2]. Fractures of the trochanteric region of the femur in young people occur as a result of the action of high-energy forces (overturning with a tractor, the effect of a firearm, traffic trauma, etc.)

There are numerous classifications of fractures of the trochanteric region of the femur. They are also divided into stable and unstable fractures. Furthermore, AO/OTA classification is most often used, while Tronz, Evans, and Jensen-Mishaels are some of the other classifications [3]. The most widely used classification today is the AO/OTA classification, created in 1987. This classification divides the trochanteric region 31-A into nine types depending on the degree of comminution. Covers most fractures of the trochanteric region within other classification systems. By classifying fractures into only three groups (A, 1-2-3), the classification itself is highly significant (Figure 1) [4].

Figure 1. AO/OTA classification and subclassification.

Methods

The methodological framework of the research in the work is subordinated to the subject, the structure of the work, and the achievement of the set goals. The research used a systematic literature review methodology based on the PRISMA Method (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses - PRISMA), using clear and predetermined inclusion and exclusion criteria. Databases such as Web of Knowledge, Scholar, and Science Direct will be accessed to search for scientific literature in English and other regional languages.

The research was conducted in January 2025. The literature review includes articles from studies published over the last 15 years. Additionally, the goal is to present intramedullary fixation of trochanter fractures as one of the most modern methods of treatment, as well as to review the experiences of other authors who have applied this technique.

In order to achieve a satisfactory reduction and to facilitate the patients' early recovery, surgical treatment is required for such kinds of fractures [5]. The dynamic hip screw (DHS) implant, which was previously regarded as the gold standard therapy for stable intertrochanteric fractures, was shown to be inadequate for the stabilisation of fractures of the unstable kind (Figure 2), [6]. As opposed to extramedullary devices such as DHS, proximal femoral nails (PFN) have a biomechanical advantage because of their closer location to the vector of force line and shorter moment arm [7]. Moreover, based on the results of several reports, intramedullary fixation may be preferable to extramedullary fixation for patients since there is a lower risk of implant failure and reoperation, and functional scores are higher [8,9,10]. It is possible to implant a PFN with a minimally invasive procedure. By performing a closed reduction of the fracture, the haematoma is maintained, and the surgeon can do a minimally invasive procedure with minimum soft-tissue dissection, thereby minimizing surgical trauma, blood loss, infec-

tion, and wound complications [11,12]. Complications of operative treatment for trochanteric femur fractures with extramedullary and intramedullary fixation include wound dehiscence, infection, pseudarthrosis, device failure, and hip joint arthrosis (Figure 4), [8-12].

Figure 2. Dynamic hip screw (DHS)

Figure 3. Types of proximal femoral nails (PFN): a) InterTAN (Intertrochanteric Antegrade Nail), b) A-PFN (Antirotational Proximal Femoral Nail), c) PROFIN (Proximal Femoral Intramedullary Nail)

Figure 4. Complications of operative treatment of intertrochanteric fracture: a) Cut – out of DHS b) Broken screws on DHS c) Cut – out of A-PFN d) Broken nail of A-PFN

Characteristics of PFNs

InterTAN (Intertrochanteric Antegrade Nail)

The titanium alloy used in the production of InterTAN PFN allows for a proximal 4° valgus offset. The nail features a trapezoidal cross-section with a 17 mm proximal diameter and a 10 to 11.5 mm grooved distal tip diameter. InterTAN PFNs are available with either a 125° or 130° collodiaphyseal angle (CDA). A lag screw of 11 mm and a compression screw of 7 mm were used. The tip of the nail was secured by a single screw that was locked in either a dynamic or static configuration. With the combined proximal screw system, it was possible to achieve interfragmentary compression of up to 15 mm. The InterTAN nail is designed with an interlocking lag nail system that helps minimise femoral head movement and prevents the femoral head from collapsing[7].

A-PFN (Antirotational Proximal Femoral Nail)

A-PFN is available in two different lengths: 160 and 220 mm. The top portion of the proximal nail features a 6° valgus angle (mediolateral curvature) with a diameter of 15 mm. This nail is available in four different diameters: 9, 10, 11, and 12; it has a lag screw that compresses the fractures and a wedge block that provides rotational stability for femoral fractures. The 10 mm wide thread and 125° angle of the lag screw are consistent with the CDA. The wedge block is in the groove on the lower portion of the lag screw. The distal end of the nail has two locking holes appropriate for either dynamic or static fixations, as well as a slot [13].

PROFIN (Proximal Femoral Intramedullary Nail)

PROFIN PFN is a titanium alloy tube with a cannulated and flat design. It features a proximal valgus offset of 6° and a distal grooved shape, and it is attached with two 8.5 mm lag screws with 135° CDA. The surgical compression of interfragmentary fractures was also possible with this system. The nail has a 16 mm diameter at its

proximal end and three separate distal diameters measuring 10, 11, and 12 mm. Both dynamic and static fixation with 4.5 mm locking screws are possible via the two distal holes [14].

Surgical Management

Before starting the application of the intramedullary nail, it is necessary to perform anatomical reduction of the fracture after introducing the patient to general or regional anesthesia on the extension table, as well as antibiotics and protection against deep vein thrombosis. After that, a 5 cm surgical incision is made above the greater trochanter, and the muscle tissue is layered with a blunt preparation. Kirschner wires - the guide is introduced into the medullary canal from the top of the greater trochanter, where it is the entry point, and the position of the wires is monitored by radiographic recording in LL and AP. Then follows reaming of the proximal femur with a 16 cm diameter reamer. After applying the intramedullary nail and visually confirming whether the anteversion of the nail is appropriate, two screws of the proper length are used in the proximal part of the nail. Proximal screws are integrated with the lower screw, 5 mm shorter than the upper one, to perform compression of the fragments. After visual confirmation that the intramedullary nail is in the appropriate position, the setting of the cortical screw in the distal edge of the nail follows in a static or dynamic position (whether we want compression or not) [15,16,17,18].

Discussion

The anatomical specificity of the proximal femur, the frequent occurrence of complications, as well as the occurrence of difficulties during fracture osteosynthesis, is an excellent challenge for operative treatment. The most adequate device is the one that can prevent medial translation of the femoral shaft, rotation, and, of course, a change in the collodiaphyseal angle. Today, in the official literature, many controversies can be found about the type of apparatus (osteosynthetic material) that is most adequate [17,18]. Meta-analyses show that the intrame-

dullary wedge achieves a short healing period and a low rate of complications compared to extramedullary fixation.

Oliveira et al. did a study with over 230 patients, where the highest number of deaths was in patients over 90 years old. In 118 patients, or 51.3% of patients, death occurred after the completion of operative treatment and implementation of rehabilitation. Only 3.5% (8 patients) died during hospitalization. Out of the total number of patients, 83.5% were women. They also found that there was an association between the duration of surgery and the death of patients after the completion of orthopedic treatment and rehabilitation ($p < 0.05$), as well as between the presence of heart disease in patients and the death of patients during hospitalization [19].

Sharma et al. proved that in the group of patients where intramedullary fixation was performed, the mean length of the incision was 4.9 cm. Still, there was a greater exposure to radiation during the operation ($p < 0.01$). It is statistically significant that the length of the operation itself was shorter when using intramedullary osteosynthesis ($p < 0.01$). Average blood loss as well as postoperative blood replacement was higher in the group operated with the DHS system compared to the group with intramedullary osteosynthesis. Although not statistically significant, the duration of hospitalization was longer in patients with extramedullary versus intramedullary osteosynthesis. They also determined that the cost of the implants themselves in extramedullary osteosynthesis was 55% of the total cost of intramedullary osteosynthesis. Due to the complexity of the instruments and the course of the operation, the incidence of technical errors was higher in the group with intramedullary osteosynthesis, 9.67% compared to the extramedullary group, where it was 3.48%. But that's why the occurrence of infection was higher in the group with extramedullary osteosynthesis. The percentage of mortality was similar in both groups, but it is stated that the cause was not related to the operation itself and occurred three months after the operation [20]. Meniscalo et al. included patients with intramedullary osteosynt-

hesis in their study. The intramedullary wedge they used is a 130° angle screw, 170mm long, and one 10mm diameter screw or two 6mm diameter screws. The percentages of rapid recovery and return to functionality are significantly high during treatment [21]. In the research by Wang et al., which included 924 patients - 486 with intramedullary and 438 with extramedullary osteosynthesis - significant data were obtained. The average age of the patients was 60 years. They found data that during intramedullary osteosynthesis, blood loss was minimal, surgical-traumatic tissue damage was minimal, and the percentage of complications was lower. But they stated that it is statistically significant that comminuted fractures can be resolved only by extramedullary osteosynthesis [22]. Wei Fu et al. compared the treatment outcomes of a patient with an intertrochanteric femoral fracture using intramedullary (PFN) and extramedullary (DHS) osteosynthesis. A retrospective study showed that separate analysis of samples leads to clear indications for operative treatment. Statistical analysis revealed that the method using the PFN device is associated with a shorter operation time and a reduced need for blood and blood product transfusions. Both techniques have demonstrated excellent clinical results [23]. Additionally, the duration of the operation and the postoperative Hip Harris score test show more favorable results with intramedullary fixation compared to extramedullary fixation. Intraoperative blood loss is lower with intramedullary fixation than with extramedullary fixation [24]. Yoo J, et al. showed that in 351 patients surgically treated with intramedullary fixation, surgical and non-surgical complications were few, including anemia and electrolyte imbalance [25]. Liu et al. showed that in 18 patients after intramedullary fixation of the proximal femur, THA was the method of choice for the treatment of arthrosis of the hip joint. The operations were successful with minimal blood loss and good results of functional tests, which is, of course, an indicator of the use of the appropriate method for femur fractures [26]. Yang et al. retrospectively analyzed 216 patients with intertrochanteric fractures treated using intramedullary fixa-

tion. They reported minimal blood loss, little deviation from the bone axis, and excellent results on functional tests [27]. Niu E and others presented that the most frequently used method is operative treatment of hip fractures. Simplicity of the surgical technique, minimal blood loss, minimal incision length, as well as shorter duration of surgery, are the features of intramedullary fixation, which makes it the first choice in operative treatment. In their study, 68% used cephalomedullary fracture fixation [28].

Saul et al. reported a success rate of 358 patients with intramedullary wedge application, which was enormous, occurring within 24 hours after the fracture. Out of the total number, as many as 46% of patients had a pertrochanteric fracture. The study showed that the longest delay time was hip surgery (28.3h) [29]. Dekhne et al. reviewed 910 patients, noting the percentage of implants requiring revision. They concluded that only 7% of patients with cephalomedullary nails required revision [30].

Bo Y and colleagues performed a reflexive analysis of unstable intertrochanteric fractures with different subdivisions. In each group, intramedullary fixation showed excellent results. $P < 0.05$ was statistically significant [31].

Kwek et al. showed that patients with unstable intertrochanteric fractures treated with intramedullary fixation had a shorter hospital stay and underwent early fracture fixation ($p < 0.001$) [32]. A group of different authors conducted studies, the results of which showed that intramedullary fixation of fractures minimized blood loss, shortened the duration of surgery, reduced pain intensity to a minimum, and led to almost ideal bone union. Comparing the four main items between different categories of implants, they concluded that the use of intramedullary fixation is the best method of choice for fracture treatment [33-40]. Li XP and co-authors performed a prospective cohort study with patients treated with intramedullary fixation. Comparing the group of patients who died with those who survived, they found that the percentage of comorbidities was higher in patients who died. [31]

Ju JB and co-authors followed 164 patients in their study. Thirty-nine patients died, and the rest were processed for further functional analysis. HHS was 71.8 ± 13.1 , and the Barthel index was 80.2 ± 18.1 . By associating the functional results with the patient's age, albumin values, and ADL, the group of authors identified the underlying factors. This will help them to modify the variable factors to achieve better outcomes and a better functional prognosis [42].

Zhong G and his co-authors performed an analysis where patients were followed for an average of 24.7 months. The patients had a per-trochanteric fracture and were treated with intramedullary fixation and arthroplasty. Comparing these two groups of patients, the time for revision, and the healing time, intraoperative blood loss, and limb shortening, HHS concluded that the results are far more favorable in patients who were treated with intramedullary fixation [43].

Sezgin EA, with a group of authors, conducted a retrospective study in Lithuania and Turkey, where 100 patients with proximal femur fractures caused by low-energy force participated. Patients were classified into nine subcategories using risk assessment tools. Comparing the functional results, they concluded that intramedullary fixation is the first choice of treatment [44]. Chee YH and co-authors studied 13 publications with 687 patients. They concluded that the average operation time, average hospital stay, and average time to surgery were shorter with intramedullary fixation [45].

Jennison T and co-authors compared the operative time and length of hospital stay in patients with a preprosthetic fracture and a fracture of the trochanteric region of the femur treated operatively with intramedullary fixation. Of course, they concluded that the time of surgery and the time of hospital stay are shorter with intramedullary fixation of proximal femur fractures [46].

Phruetthiphath OA et al found that an integrated scoring system (ISSI score) developed based on surgical and medical techniques, due to its high specificity and sensitivity, its results can be

used for the evaluation and treatment of patients with intertrochanteric fractures treated with PFNA fixation [47]. Qin Y and his authors proved that THA is a very effective method of hip salvage after failed intramedullary fixation. However, it should be emphasized that the preoperative risk and complications are high [48].

Su Z, together with his co-authors, conducted a study comparing InterTan and PFN. The study included 75 cases. In the results of the study, no significant difference can be observed in the gender composition, age, fracture site, type of AO, anesthesia method, fracture reduction, and distance from the tip between the InterTan group and the PFNA group. This is an indication that intramedullary fixation (regardless of which osteosynthetic material is used) is the first choice for the treatment of fractures of the proximal end of the femur [49].

Conclusion

Surgically treated fractures of the trochanter region with intramedullary fixation are now the preferred method. The small surgical incision, lower intraoperative blood loss, and reduced complication rates are consistent with this approach.

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